

**Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science
End of Year Report
2019-2020**

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Our Mission

The Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science (AVDS) focuses on one central mission - to increase racial and ethnic equity within the research programs at Oregon Health and Science University (OHSU) by recruiting, retaining, and most importantly, supporting graduate students, postdoctoral scholars, staff, and faculty members from underrepresented backgrounds.

A note about current times

This year we are witnessing national protests in opposition to police brutality against the Black community sparked by the murder of George Floyd. Like many of you, we feel overwhelmed with complex emotions. On top of a global health pandemic, we continue to encounter the disgusting brutality and dehumanization of Black lives by institutions that claim to “protect and serve.” While these injustices recently gained renewed visibility, they are not new for BIPOC (Black, Indigenous, and People of Color). Despite these devastating challenges, a key aspect to social justice work involves maintaining an unwavering belief and dedication to the possibility for change. The radical and critically important movement leader, Angela Davis, said it best:

***“You have to act as if it were possible to radically transform the world.
And you have to do it all the time.”***

This truth continues to guide our work. To support the Black Lives Matter (BLM) movement and respond to the increased interest in engaging with racial equity work, AVDS hosted a virtual community forum for over 220 OHSU employees, titled **“Racial Justice Allyship,”** to discuss dismantling systemic racism. We spoke bluntly about the ways in which white supremacy guides and manifests in our culture and institutions, and discussed actionable first steps for someone new to racial equity work. AVDS also put together a page of [anti-racism resources](#). In addition, AVDS collaborated with [Women in Science PDX \(WIS PDX\)](#) to fundraise for the **PDX Protest Bail Fund** to directly support local protests. WIS PDX generously matched all donations up to \$1000, resulting in a total of \$2115 raised to support our local community in the fight against police brutality. Finally, we **redistributed our excess funds** from donations to local organizations supporting Black justice work, which received approximately \$300 each:

Our approach to addressing racial equity

AVDS takes a two-pronged approach to addressing racial equity, through **community building** and **policy change**. **Community building** is necessary to allow organic exposure to racial equity work that then fosters engagement. **Policy change** can be leveraged to build anti-racist systems and support grassroots culture shifts. Both approaches are essential components to racial equity work.

Our past accomplishments

As this is AVDS' inaugural annual report, we will first highlight our accomplishments to date. One essential purpose of this document is to practice transparency. We also hope that this document will be informative for those who either support our work or start their own grassroots anti-racism projects. Please visit the [AVDS website](#), where you can sign up for our monthly newsletter, donate, send us inquiries, and explore our resources.

Founded in 2016, AVDS is a group of volunteers including students, staff, postdocs, and faculty at Oregon Health & Science University (OHSU) in Portland, Oregon (U.S.) who work together to fulfill our mission, as stated above. AVDS achieves its mission by taking a two-pronged approach: working with administration to change policies that uphold systemic and institutional racism, and building community to improve the culture of inclusion. From the

beginning, AVDS has emphasized the importance of retention of underrepresented racial minority (URM) scientists, rather than focusing on traditional “pipeline/pathway” programs of URM recruitment, for example. At OHSU, there are many outreach programs designed to illuminate career paths in healthcare and STEM, provide opportunities to URM learners, and ultimately recruit these participants into graduate and professional training programs. While AVDS acknowledges that those efforts are important and necessary, we believe that by first cultivating an environment of equity and inclusion at OHSU, we can recruit URM candidates into a safe and welcoming community for a sustainable and fair vision of diversity.

AVDS advocates for change by meeting regularly with administrators and faculty to discuss and implement anti-racist policies. Our document, [Recommendations for increasing and supporting racial diversity](#)¹, is an early example of our policy efforts, and was developed in response to OHSU’s desire to strengthen an educational relationship with the University of Maryland, Baltimore (UMBC). AVDS was invited to meet with Dr. Freeman Hrabowski, UMBC’s President, during his visit to OHSU; however, our members believed that our graduate programs and research departments needed to make substantive progress towards addressing systemic racism before recruiting UMBC students, who are mostly people of color, to OHSU. As a result, OHSU leadership coordinating Dr. Hrabowski’s visit asked AVDS for recommendations to improve diversity and inclusion at OHSU. The resulting document was presented in March 2018.

Since 2018, the School of Medicine and Chief Research Officer have acted on the following recommendations:

- Creating a part-time Dean of Diversity position
- Providing funds for invited guest speakers
- Collecting data on underrepresented minority retention
- Compiling the first annual diversity report
- Supporting a pilot Neuroscience Postbaccalaureate training opportunity for underrepresented minorities (*funded by the Chief Research Officer, with the Vollum Institute and the Department of Behavioral Neuroscience*)

To promote community-building, AVDS hosts events on a yearly, quarterly, monthly and weekly basis that allow us to provide educational opportunities and engage with the OHSU community. Examples include a monthly happy hour, weekly book club discussions, quarterly documentary showings, an annual invited speaker, and more. AVDS also attends the yearly recruitment events for most of OHSU’s graduate research programs in order to welcome each applicant (170+ recruits in 2020 alone) and give historically minoritized recruits a resource for understanding the culture at OHSU. Finally, to further strengthen our relationships with

departments and programs, we created liaison positions which allows AVDS to understand and influence each unit's racial equity policies, procedures, and culture.

AVDS was founded by four individuals. Nearly four years later, we have an eight-member executive board, five committees with a sixth in development, and over 40 active members. We frequently collaborate and/or receive regular funding from the OHSU School of Medicine, the Vollum Institute, Graduate Student Organization, Women In Science PDX, the OHSU Black Employee Resource Group, OHSU Graduate Programs, the Center for Diversity and Inclusion, OnTrack, and *many* more. Finally, our monthly newsletter has over 400 subscribers, and we are active on social media.

Our mission is far from over, but we hope that recent events have persuaded people to recognize that our institution, along with so many others, needs drastic change in order to break out of the holding patterns that have kept systemic racism alive for centuries. With our community of supporters, we will continue our efforts to dismantle systemic racism and white supremacy and work towards an anti-racist institution.

Our 2019-2020 Report

Committee Members 2019-2020

Events	Education	Operations	Communications
Mateo Lopez Espejo	Katy Lehmann	Itallia V. Pacentine	Tavita Garrett
Dennis Weingarten	Kathleen Beeson	Eric Earl	Eleanor Battison
Molly Campbell	Jennifer Cai	Anthony Galassi	Robin Champieux
Cole Brashaw	Robert Hermosillo	Mason Handford	Kim Englen
Hannah Fulenwider	Brian Karlberg	Alexandra Houser	Amanda del Giacco
Ozama Ismail	Sarah Kisiwaa	Dave Jacobs	Jennifer Jahncke
Michelle Kielhold	Danielle Mathieson	Omar Koita	Alina Krollenbock
Kylene Lowrey	Allison Schaser	Ernesto Manzo	Katy Lehmann
	Sierra Smith	AJ Mitchell	Melissa Merrigan
	Amanda Swanson	Lucille Moore	Gabriel Romero
		M. Kathrina Onate	
		Nithya Ramalingam	
		Erica Hankins Regalo	
		Kristen Stevens	

Board Members 2019-2020

- Sierra Smith - *Receptionist*
- Teresa Stackhouse – *Treasurer*
- Arielle Isakharov – *Secretary*
- Letisha Wyatt - *Historian*
- Mateo Lopez Espejo - *Events Committee Chair*
- Katy Lehmann - *Education Committee Chair*
- Itallia V. Pacentine, PhD - *Operations Committee Chair*
- Tavita Garrett - *Communications Committee Chair*

Message from the Board

This year marks a new chapter in the history of the Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science. We implemented a decentralized power structure, reflecting our learning about how to organize our rapidly growing group, and feel immense pride in the hard work accomplished by our members. Their dedication and volunteerism allowed us to meet all of our goals: increasing the presence of AVDS on campus; expanding our membership; establishing the faculty committee and liaisons; implementing a new Game Night event; and improving our relationships with other groups on campus. We look forward to continuing to work with our incredible volunteers to champion even more progress in the coming year.

The importance of restructuring AVDS

Academic year 2019-2020 was the first in which AVDS operated under a decentralized power structure. Prior to 2019, AVDS used a centralized and hierarchical leadership model, with a president positioned at the top, a board underneath this, and several committees reporting to the board. Like many new groups, we defaulted to using a Western, centralized and hierarchical leadership model without a full understanding of the values and ideals it reflected and drove. This model puts the voice of the president and the board above the voices of the larger group and can demotivate those with less positional power. This was in contrast to the equitable structure AVDS sought to build, wherein all voices were heard, valued and empowered.

In addition to equity, AVDS strives for longevity. Centralized leadership, especially in social justice groups, often revolves around a charismatic and passionate leader.² Although seemingly beneficial, this style poses a danger. When a charismatic leader drives a movement or group, it becomes susceptible to disassembling when the leader leaves.² Moreover, history provides examples of how targeting charismatic leaders halts social justice progress, including Reverend Dr. Martin Luther King and the leaders of the Black Panther Party, such as Fred Hampton. In an academic setting, having a centralized structure with a student as president threatens the longevity of AVDS because students graduate.

Recognizing how a hierarchical and centralized leadership model hurt our goals and contrasted with our values, we removed the president position. While our [current model](#) (figure to the right) does include aspects of hierarchical organization, as our committees are chaired by 1-2 individuals, the chairs do not hold more power than the committee members. The role of the chair(s) is to help their team organize to carry out action items that are mutually agreed upon. Ultimately, the restructuring process allowed us to understand and shift away from systems designed to withhold power from others. We hope that documenting this journey provides an example of how such tools of oppression are omnipresent in our society, and how to conscientiously identify and rectify use of those tools within an organization.

***We all must remain vigilant in identifying tools of oppression
and remain open to shifting towards something better.***

A year of great achievement

This year AVDS experienced a large increase in membership, community engagement, and committee involvement. Our committees worked to advance our mission through events, strengthening our internal organization, and forming the Policy Task Force. Below we highlight the achievements of our organization and each committee over the last year and discuss their future directions.

The number of community members opting in to receive our newsletter has been growing steadily since 2017 (see graph to the right). In 2020, we are on track to meet or exceed our historical yearly member growth rate. Our committee sizes have also been increasing steadily (see plot below). Please note that while our organization formed in 2016, the graph reflects when we began collecting data on our subscriber numbers in 2017 and establishment of committees in 2018.

AVDS newsletter subscribers by year

Committee Size Growth 2018-2020

Budget

Sources of Funding

The majority of our funding (79%) comes from various departments within Oregon Health & Science University. The rest of our funding (21%) is community support - whether through donations to our website or contributions made by attendees at our Happy Hours.

Funding Allocation

We believe that an institutional/organizational budget is a moral document. Decisions about what you spend funds on and where you spend them should be thoughtful, transparent and mission-aligned. We spend funds to provide resources to advance our missions of **community building** and **policy change**.

COMMUNITY BUILDING

How do we build and empower our community?

AVDS works to build community in a way that creates avenues for everyone to become involved no matter their level of knowledge or experience. We believe that grassroots community engagement creates a greatly needed space to allow for critical conversations regarding race. By increasing opportunities for engagement, we help promote the necessary realization of the personal responsibility needed for progress. Our committees include representation from nearly all research positions at OHSU, from staff to trainees to faculty, and span several OHSU departments.

AVDS makeup by OHSU position

Our **Events, Education, and Communications Committees** carry out a large part of our focus on community building. We highlight their achievements here:

Events Committee

The Events Committee focuses on creating a space for education and conversation around racism, as well expanding our community to empower people to become engaged and to dismantle the systemic racism that permeates our institutions and lives. We discuss critical issues surrounding race and question our biases, all while having a great time. Our recurring events this year included:

AVDS Happy Hour

We hold happy hours on the last Friday of the month. OHSU is a large institution, so siloing of schools and departments is common. To counteract this, we foster spaces for community building by opening our events to all. Funding from the Vollum Institute supplies refreshments. These events attract more than 30 attendees on average and are a great place to relax and meet new colleagues!

AVDS Board Game Night

We get together the second Friday of each month to spend some time socializing and playing games. The goal of these gatherings is to connect OHSU students, employees, and faculty from various departments on campus in a low-pressure environment.

Graduate Program Recruitment

AVDS attends OHSU's graduate student recruitment events to provide information and personal perspectives on the experience of student life at OHSU and in Portland. We invite prospective students to send us questions that are then answered by current students who identify as URMs. We strive to provide recruits with the information they need to make the decision that is best for them!

Future goals

We aim to expand the spaces and opportunities to connect with each other. Due to COVID-19, we had to cancel many of our annual social events including a postdoc community discussion and Karaoke Night and Arcade Game Night, which we host in collaboration with the Graduate Student Organization and the School of Medicine. We are working to transition these events online or create new events conducive to an online environment.

Education Committee

The Education Committee provides educational opportunities critical for deconstructing systemic with a focus on understanding the of race/racism and its many current manifestations.

Racial Justice Accomplice Training

To kick off the academic year we hosted a two-hour Racial Justice Accomplice Training for 20 members of the OHSU community. Led by Dr. Bevyn Rowland, the workshop explored ways of being an active, rather than passive, ally to people of color and steps to go beyond “allyship.” We also discussed how to address our own white fragility using resources and training from invited speakers hosted by local Portland universities.

Quarterly Documentary Screenings

It is impossible to understand systemic racism without a historical framework, particularly one that reveals the histories of oppressed populations. We host **quarterly documentary screenings** and discussions. This year, we showed the following documentaries:

Admissions on Trial, Seven Decades of Race in Higher Education - Documents the complexities of Affirmative Action and diversity and equity initiatives.

Local Color - A history of racism in Oregon, screened for Dr. Martin Luther King Jr. Day.

Dolores - Chronicles the life of Dolores Huerta, co-founder of the first farm workers union. Hosted in partnership with WIS PDX in honor of César Chávez Day (*postponed due to COVID-19*).

AVDS Book Club

We host a **book club** series with the goal of learning and fostering conversations regarding race/racism. The OHSU Center for Diversity and Inclusion generously bought books and provided refreshments for these discussions. We started with *White Fragility* by Robin Diangelo followed by *How to be an Antiracist* by Ibram X Kendi, giving us an opportunity to learn about racism from the perspective of a Black man. Due to COVID-19, we moved to a virtual format for our next book, *The Case for Reparations* by Ta-Nehisi Coates. This spurred discussions about the Black Lives Matter movement and the racist history of policing. We recently expanded to discussing articles and podcasts chosen by participants, encouraging people to take on leadership roles and allowing us to apply our knowledge to current societal context. All attendees stated that bookclub was essential in their journey to becoming anti-racist.

Nonviolent Communication Training

Finally, the Education Committee hosted a 4-week **Nonviolent Communication training** in July attended by over 20 participants. Conversations around race can be charged and difficult to navigate. By practicing skills in nonviolent communication (NVC) as well as de-escalation and conflict transformation techniques, participants learned how to hold challenging conversations, communicate clearly and compassionately, and transform conflict. The course was taught by The Center of Restorative Solutions in Seattle and sponsored by the Howard Hughes Medical Institute Gilliam Fellowship.

Future goals

AVDS normally hosts an **annual guest speaker**, supported by a \$1500 commitment from the School of Medicine. We typically invite speakers to discuss diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) in science. However, we also want to value and center the scientific contributions of BIPOC researchers. This year, we invited **Dr. Tirin Moore**, Professor of Neurology at Stanford University. Dr. Moore studies the neural basis of cognition using primates and computational science and we felt his work would appeal to trainees and faculty across basic, translational, and clinical research. While Dr. Moore's visit was postponed due to COVID-19, we plan to host his talk virtually in January 2021. Finally, the committee plans to also host online movie and discussion nights.

Communications Committee

This year the Communications Committee focused on improving communication within OHSU as well broadening our outreach to the larger Pacific Northwest, academic, and social justice communities via Twitter. Some highlights from the year include:

Website

Our website houses information about AVDS including our written recommendations for dismantling systemic racism at OHSU, events hosted by us and others, and resources, particularly for incoming students. Along with general maintenance, we added a timeline to showcase our activities and accomplishments. This year, we experienced an increase in traffic to our site of more than 1000%, coinciding with growing interest in our group and racial equity in academia (see figure to right). The geographical location of site visitors spans the entire US (see figure below, created using Google Analytics).

AVDS monthly website traffic

Total # of new website visitors 2019-2020

Monthly newsletter

Our newsletter provides a way for our larger membership to stay informed of and involved with AVDS. We promote diversity-related events, share general news, resources and funding opportunities, and highlight individual AVDS members' accomplishments. This year, we reached a total of 465 subscribers (see [Cumulative Subscribers figure](#) on page 9).

Social Media

This year, we expanded our Twitter following and connected with other groups with similar goals. We also started an Instagram account where we share educational content on topics such as structural racism and history. Follow us on Twitter & Instagram at:

@A4VDiS

@a4vdis

Email Standard of Protocol

AVDS regularly receives emails regarding DEI needs at OHSU. As a volunteer-based group, we strategically evaluate each request to determine if it falls within our mission or if other groups are better suited to meet the need. We developed a standard reply protocol in order to ensure our responses maximize positive outcomes while adhering to the goals of our mission and respecting the capacity of our members.

Future goals

The Communications Committee will continue to grow our social media presence to further engage with the OHSU community. Specifically, we want to grow our Instagram page to include bite-size educational resources as well as profiles of AVDS members to highlight their interests and motivations for joining the group. Additionally, we plan to develop surveys to gather feedback on AVDS events and priorities, as well as potential OHSU leadership actions.

Establishment of the AVDS Lounge

The creation of an **AVDS Lounge** marked another highlight of the year. Generously gifted by the Vollum Institute, the lounge is a space for AVDS members to hang out, study, and use for AVDS meetings. We are furnishing and painting the space and have commissioned a Black artist, [Dennis Bonsu](#), to create a mural that depicts the spirit of solidarity AVDS strives to cultivate.

Recognizing the Efforts of our Members

AVDS understands that in order to shift the culture at OHSU, active engagement and a sense of shared responsibility by all members of the OHSU community is required. Often, the burden of this work falls largely on volunteers from marginalized backgrounds. As this work often goes unrecognized and does not count towards the completion of degrees or promotion, the inequities experienced by these volunteers are often further perpetuated. AVDS could not have achieved anything without the collective efforts of our volunteers, and we are sincerely grateful to all who have volunteered their time, efforts, and skills towards bettering the environment at OHSU.

POLICY CHANGE

A racial equity lens to guide policy change

Addressing formal policies and practices that uphold systemic racism is the second focus of the racial justice work AVDS prioritizes. OHSU, like all large organizations, integrates formal policies into programs, departments, centers, and institutes. In order to create racially equitable policies, a racial equity framework must be used. Without this, we risk implementing inequitable policies and practices. Examples of such inequities include disparities in the recruitment of faculty, staff, and students; lack of financial prioritization in addressing systemic racism; and pay inequities across racial groups. When we use a racial equity lens to evaluate our actions at all levels, many areas of improvement emerge. The combined efforts of our **Operations Committee, Policy Task Force, and Faculty Committee** carry out AVDS' policy work:

Operations Committee

The Operations Committee is responsible for addressing the internal operations of AVDS and assessing our impact at OHSU. Operations organizes and works with departmental and student group liaisons to familiarize us with programs across OHSU. The committee uses this information as well as internal AVDS data to assess our impact and reach.

Internal Operations

We organized an AVDS presence at the recruitment drives for nearly every PhD program, created the first AVDS Annual Report, and prepared the new AVDS Lounge for public opening. We also curated a list of chairs and administrators of programs and departments throughout OHSU to facilitate easier contact with the leadership and administration of OHSU.

Liaisons

We established program/department liaisons to build relationships across campus.

Internal Data Analysis

We standardized AVDS sign-in sheets and surveys, analyzed the data collected from these sources, created a GitHub repository for AVDS data, and created an open-source directory for larger OHSU outreach efforts to target Oregon schools with high percentages of Black students (a BLM initiative developed by committee member AJ Mitchell). Additionally, we participated in the revision of the OHSU School of Medicine Diversity Action Plan and evaluated the School of Medicine's first Annual Diversity Report.

Future goals

We plan to share a collection of resources online that will enable people from other institutions to start their own racial equity groups. Students from across the country continue

to reach out to us for advice, and we believe the structure and principles of our group may help those who see the value of grassroots organization. Regarding internal data, we will further develop our GitHub repository and automated methods for quantifying and visualizing our data. We will also expand our data collection to include more metrics to track our progress, including community feedback to inform community and evidence-based decision making.

Formation of Policy Task Force and AVDS Faculty Committee

One of the things that makes AVDS unique is that we prioritize involvement in institutional policies to cultivate racial equity and inclusion. Traditionally, our board members were responsible for improving racial equity policies at OHSU by working directly with administration. As AVDS grew, we decided to re-allocate this work to the **Policy Task Force**. This new committee allows more members to be involved in shaping OHSU policies pertaining to racial equity and effectively crowdsources the heavy workload of making policy changes. In addition to the Policy Task Force, we recently formed an **AVDS Faculty Committee**, which provides faculty members an opportunity to be involved with AVDS and a space to collaborate around issues that they are in a unique position to address.

While new, in July 2020, the Policy Task Force helped publish a proposal, written by Antoinette Foster and Dr. Letisha Wyatt (both co-founders of AVDS), titled [Revisiting OHSU's approach to racial diversity, equity, and inclusion](#).³ It calls for the creation of “Racial Equity and Inclusion (REI)” Centers embedded in departments throughout OHSU to engage specific communities, informed by the way AVDS has engaged sectors of the research community. This structure focuses on deconstructing systemic racism through a racial equity lens to create innovative solutions specific to each community’s needs.

Systemic racism manifests at the individual, interpersonal, institutional and structural levels⁴, each of which need to be addressed specifically and directly. In order to do this, we suggested that each REI center have at least three central positions that focus on the four aforementioned levels of systemic racism. To the best of our knowledge, this is a novel approach to structuring diversity efforts. **OHSU’s Chief Research Officer has committed to piloting a REI center to test and fine-tune the approach.** AVDS presented our proposal to the OHSU Board of Directors and will continue to push for the adoption of this radical new model that compensates those who work on racial equity at OHSU, appropriately distributes the work across the OHSU community to establish a shared sense of responsibility, and uses a data-driven, evidence-based approach to creating equitable policy community.

Future goals

In the upcoming year we will establish chairs and group-directed goals for each new committee. The Policy Task Force will continue to guide the School of Medicine in revising their Diversity Action Plan and Annual Diversity Report (previously handled by the Operations Committee) and continue to promote formation of REI Centers. The Faculty Committee will focus on racial equity policies for faculty as well as policies impacting students and staff in their departments and programs. AVDS will empower and support the critical work the Faculty Committee carries out by guiding and providing educational resources.

What's next for AVDS?

Since 2016, AVDS has focused on dismantling racial inequities within our communities, specifically within graduate research programs at OHSU. COVID-19 and the renewed attention to ways in which racism and white supremacy are embedded into American and global culture and policies highlight social inequities in clear and devastating ways. Recent events also demonstrate the intersection of inequities often compounded for people of color (e.g. at the intersection of race and wealth), which underscores the need to look at all aspects of life through the lens of racial equity. Indeed, these problems arise in every space we find ourselves in, including science.

Over the upcoming academic year, we will continue to work with our community to dismantle systemic racism and the inequities that intersect with race. We feel ecstatic and encouraged by the increase in participation and the dedication of individuals wanting to advance racial justice. The first step in transforming our communities is for the community to decide it is ready to transform; the next step is doing the work to ensure transformation. Together we can reflect, innovate, and transform ourselves and our environments into an equitable community for all.

How to get involved

We are always looking for more dedicated individuals to join our team! Please fill out our [interest form](#) and we will get back to you!

If you have limited time, you can also keep up with us by [signing up for our newsletter](#) or help our cause by [donating](#)!

References

- 1 Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science. (2018, May 1). Recommendations for Increasing and Supporting Racial Diversity (2017 - 2018). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3948281>
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- 4 The Lens of Systemic Oppression. (2020, August, 6). Retrieved from <https://www.nationalequityproject.org/frameworks/lens-of-systemic-oppression>